

CATALYTIC HYDRATION OF ACETYLENE IN VAPOR PHASE

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M.G. Hydration of acetylene (and its derivatives) in a solution of Hg (II) salts, which was discovered by Kucherov in 1881, has been important in industrial organic synthesis for a long time. Catalytic triplet hydration is the most common synthesis method in synthetic chemistry and can again be an important industrial process under certain conditions when mercury-free catalysts and diluted acetylene are used. Today, the annual need for acetone in the world is 2 million tons, and the annual need for acetone in our country is 10-15 thousand tons. In developed countries, acetone is mainly obtained in several ways:

1. Oxidation and hydrogenation of isopropyl alcohol

2. Oxidation of isopropyl benzene (Kumol method)

3. Acetylene hydration

Activation was carried out by conventional acid activation method at 10-20% acid concentration at approximately 60% consumption, with a solid-to-liquid ratio of 1:3 to 1:5, depending on the duration of the process. It took 2-4 hours, washing and grinding of the finished product was carried out depending on its intended direction. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Change of main components in acid activation

Activation time, hours	Acid concentration, H ₂ SO ₄						Acid concentration, HCl					
	10		15		20		10		15		20	
	Content, %						Content, %					
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃
2	62,3	18,7	63,1	18,4	63,5	17,8	61,9	17,9	62,4	17,1	63,5	16,8
4	67,5	17,4	68,8	15,5	68,6	14,5	66,6	16,4	67,2	16,1	66,5	15,6
6	71,8	14,9	73,8	13,4	75,7	12,6	70,2	15,9	72,4	14,4	73,8	13,7
8	80,3	12,2	81,7	11,5	82,4	10,4	75,4	14,3	76,5	13,8	77,2	13,1

As can be seen from Table 1, after acid activation of clays, their chemical composition and, accordingly, their crystal structure underwent significant changes, which can be seen by the increase in SiO₂ content and a sharp decrease in Al₂O₃ in the samples.

The processing of Navbahor modified bentonite at temperatures above 700 °C leads to the release of water between the layers and the deterioration of textural properties with irreversible adhesion of the layers. However, as can be seen from the figures (Figure 1), no significant changes were observed in the pore structure parameters of the initial clay samples in the heating temperature range of 70-500°C.

Figure 1. Effect of heating temperature on the surface of bentonite

The morphology of the catalysts was studied using wave electron microscopy (ZEM) at Vegall LMU (Czech Republic). Also, the porous structure was established based on the analysis of the adsorption curves obtained by the thermosorption method of nitrogen. The surface area of the catalytic system was determined by the Ssol=BET method, and the volume of micro- and mesopores was determined by the BJH method.

Table 2. Composition and properties of synthesized zinc-iron-chromium-manganese-vanadium/HSZ catalysts (T=698-703 K)

Nº	Catalyst composition, mass %	Relative surface area, m²/g	Operating time until regeneration, hours	Productivity, g/kg, kat·h	Conversion of acetylene, %
1	ZnO·Fe ₂ O ₃ / HSZ	230	150	180	56
2	ZnO·Cr ₂ O ₃ / HSZ	220	160	165	78

3	ZnO·Fe ₂ O ₃ ·MnO ₂ / HSZ	135	195	190	80
4	ZnO·Cr ₂ O ₃ ·MnO ₂ / HSZ	151	200	170	84
5	ZnO·Fe ₂ O ₃ ·Cr ₂ O ₃ / HSZ	183	220	178	86
6	ZnO·Fe ₂ O ₃ ·Cr ₂ O ₃ ·MnO ₂ / HSZ	201	235	182	82
7	ZnO·Fe ₂ O ₃ ·MnO ₂ ·V ₂ O ₅ / HSZ	195	260	167	84
8	ZnO·Cr ₂ O ₃ ·MnO ₂ ·V ₂ O ₅ / HSZ	200	275	174	78
9	ZnO·Fe₂O₃·Cr₂O₃·MnO₂·V₂O₅/YuKS	205	300	330	97.2
10	ZnO·Co ₂ O ₃ ·Cr ₂ O ₃ ·MnO ₂ ·V ₂ O ₅ / HSZ	185	270	192	87
11	ZnO·Co ₂ O ₃ ·Cr ₂ O ₃ ·Mn ₂ O ₃ ·V ₂ O ₅ / HSZ	155	260	187	83
12	ZnO·Fe ₂ O ₃ ·Cr ₂ O ₃ ·Mn ₂ O ₃ ·V ₂ O ₅ / HSZ	140	250	195	88

As can be seen from Table 2, given catalysts provide high acetylene conversion. Their stability is 1-1.5 times lower than zinc-iron-chromium-manganese-vanadium/YuKS catalyst.

When the effect of temperature was studied in the range of 10-500°C, it was found that the conversion of acetylene increases and the selectivity of acetone decreases with increasing temperature. The obtained results are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Effect of temperature on acetone yield

As a result of the study of the effect of temperature on the yield of acetone, it was found that the relationship between the yield of the reaction and the temperature in the range of 10-500°C has an extreme character, and the yield has a maximum value at 425-430°C.

Based on the results of the experiment and the qualitative and quantitative composition of the reaction products, the following mechanism of acetone

formation in the presence of the given catalyst was proposed. The formation of acetone can be expressed in the form of the following cumulative equation:

We explain the formation of acetylene based on the following plausible mechanism, first acetylene is hydrated and acetaldehyde is formed:

Acetaldehyde reacts with water vapor to form acetone.

The above-mentioned method of obtaining acetone is a promising method for Uzbekistan.

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